

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STUDY ON THE ACTION OF 9 NATURAL PRODUCTS AND COLLOIDAL COPPER SOLUTION ON CANDIDA ALBICANS CULTURES

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Abstract

The work highlights the action of 9 natural substances and the colloidal Cu solution on *Candida Albicans* cultures. Observations were made at time intervals of 24, 48, 72, 96 and 120 hours. We noticed favorable results in the inhibition of *Candida Albicans* cultures after applying oregano oil, respectively copper colloidal solution, as well as cinnamon and geranium oils, for a short period of time. *Candida albicans* cultures remained unchanged in contact with the oils of: white musk, hemp, opium, cultivated thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*) and sandalwood, in a concentration of 20 %, as well as in contact with liquorice tincture (roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*).

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, *Candida* spp, culture medium, methylene blue, essential oil, tincture, culture plates.

Abbreviations: h- hour, ATCC – standard culture of *Candida albicans*, µl - microliters, Cu = copper.

Introduction

In the last two decades, hospitals have been experiencing a real and dramatic increase in nosocomial fungal infections. The most frequent pathogenic fungi involved are: *Candida* spp., *Aspergillus* spp., *Zygomycetes*. *Cryptococcus* spp. is one of the genera frequently involved in systemic infections, which reflects the large number of HIV-infected patients in the period preceding the introduction of highly active antiretroviral therapy (89% of patients with systemic infections with *Cryptococcus noformans* were HIV+) ¹. *Candida albicans* can cause superficial infections of mucous membranes and skin and deep infections of internal organs (endocarditis, meningitis, etc.) in conditions of immunodepression ².

Cutaneous-mucosal candidiasis is a superficial cutaneous or mucosal fungal infection, located more frequently in the skin folds, interdigital and periungual, in the penis or vagina ³. Oral candidomycosis or candidal stomatitis is the most common and occurs in infants, due to the lack of salivary secretion that does not begin until 2 months after birth. In adults, it occurs more frequently in diabetics, tuberculous, cachectic or immunosuppressed patients (AIDS) and post-therapeutically (after antibiotic therapy, corticotherapy, immunosuppressants). At the same time, poor oral hygiene, tooth decay and dentures, as well as acidic pH are favorable causes. Chronic diffuse candidomycosis mainly affects elderly men and affects the scalp, face, mucous membrane of the oral cavity, nails and integuments of the limbs. The lesions can sometimes have a hepatic or vegetative appearance. Systemic candidiasis occurs in immunocompromised patients (AIDS), in the form of

Candida septicemia, with the source of contamination being the digestive tract. It manifests itself with altered general condition, persistent fever, positive blood cultures and urine cultures.

Different organs can be altered: kidneys, liver, lungs, eyes, heart. At the skin level, macules, papules, follicular pustules, nodules, ulcerations may appear. Deep skin mycoses are rare conditions in our country, produced by dimorphic fungi; examples: actinomycosis, sporotrichosis, mycetoma, histoplasmosis, aspergillosis, cryptococcosis ⁴. Yeasts and fungi present in the environment enter the human body through inhalation, ingestion and posttraumatic skin inoculation, initiating infections located in the lung, paranasal sinuses, skin tissue. Some community-acquired mycoses can cause life-threatening infections, especially in immunocompromised patients ⁵. The most common infection in America and parts of Europe is caused by anthropophilic dermatophytes ⁶.

Identification of dermatophytes is a complex endeavor involving the collaboration of clinical, epidemiological and laboratory data. Direct microscopic examination is mandatory; it has intrinsic diagnostic value, as it allows the rapid confirmation of the suspicion of dermatophytic infection and the early information of the clinician, long before the positivity of the culture ⁷. Candidomycoses represent conditions produced by *Candida albicans* with multiple locations and as many clinical forms ⁸.

The development of drugs to effectively combat fungal infections is one of the ongoing concerns of the medical world ⁹.

Some of the most well-known plants used empirically as antifungals have been systematically studied, and the compounds in their structure with biological action¹⁰ have been well characterized¹¹.

Material and methods

The study was conducted over 5 days between January 15 and 20, 2020 at the "Provita 2000 Medical Center" Clinic in Constanța. The purpose of the study was to investigate several products, natural and one chemical, in the treatment of *Candida albicans*. To highlight the action of natural products on *Candida albicans* cultures, I used the Sabouraud standard culture medium on which I sowed samples of *Candida albicans*, from a calibrated assortment, called ATCC 60193. I put the plates in the thermostat, at the standard temperature of 37 °C¹². In the present study, we carried out several experiments during 120 hours, using both

natural products (essential oils, tinctures, etc.) and chemical products (colloidal Cu solution) in order to discover the substances with antifungal action on *Candida albicans* cultures. We prepared the analyzed substances in the studio, in different dilutions; then, we analyzed the size of the diameter of the zones of inhibition and lysis of the mycelial colony at different time intervals (at 24 hours, at 48 hours and 72 hours¹², 96 h and 120 h, respectively).

Results

5 days experiment

In this study I used 800 µl physiological serum + 200 µl essential oil. I seeded on Sabouraud medium.

We thermostated the cultures for 120 h, at temperature of 37°C. We performed readings and interpretations at 24 h, 48 h, 72 h, 96 h and 120 h.

Figure 1(a, b, c). Culture plates seeded with *Candida albicans* to which were applied oils of white musk, cinnamon, geranium, hemp, opium, thyme, oregano and sandalwood, in a concentration of 20 % and licorice tincture, respectively colloidal copper solution

After 24 hours of inoculation *Candida albicans* cultures show sensitivity to cinnamon oil compared to white musk oil and hemp oil. The colloidal copper solution also shows fungicidal action 24 hours after seeding, compared to the oils: opium, cultivated thyme and licorice tincture. Oregano oil inhibited *Candida albicans* cultures 24 hours after application compared to sandalwood oil.

24 hours after the application, I made slides stained with methylene blue, which I analyzed under the optical microscope, with a 40x objective.

We visualized the slides under the optical microscope for the substances that showed sensitivity on the first day.

Figure 2(a, b, c, d). Mycelial cultures to which cinnamon, oregano, geranium oils were applied, respectively colloidal copper solution after thermostating for 24 hours, examined under an optical microscope with a 100x objective

A reduction of the mycelia is observed in the first 24 hours in the case of geranium and oregano oil versus colloidal copper solution and cinnamon oil.

Figure 3(a, b, c). Culture plates inoculated with *Candida albicans* to which oils of white musk, cinnamon, geranium, hemp, opium, cultivated thyme, oregano and sandalwood in 20% concentration and wood tincture were applied sweet, respectively colloidal copper solution at 48 h

In cinnamon and geranium, sensitivity can be observed 48 h after sowing compared to the oils of: white musk and hemp. The 4 substances: opium oil, colloidal Cu solution, licorice tincture and cultivated thyme oil do not inhibit the development of candida 48 hours after seeding. *Candida albicans* is sensitive to oil of oregano 48 hours after seeding compared to oil of sandalwood.

Figure 4(a, b, c). Culture plates inoculated with *Candida albicans* to which oils of white musk, cinnamon, geranium, hemp, opium, cultivated thyme, oregano and sandalwood at a concentration of 20% and tincture were applied of licorice, respectively colloidal copper solution at 72 h

After 72 h from seeding, of all the substances used in the study, oregano oil inhibited the development of *Candida albicans* and, to a lesser extent, the colloidal Cu solution. Thus, we observed the two plates with the respective substances under the microscope.

Figure 5(a, b). Mycelial cultures on which oregano and cinnamon oils were applied, after thermostating for 72 hours, examined under the optical microscope with a 100x objective We could observe under the microscope the decrease in the number of mycelia in the case of oregano oil and of its growth for cinnamon oil after 3 days of thermostating.

Figure 6(a, b, c). Culture plates inoculated with *Candida albicans* to which oils of white musk, cinnamon, geranium, hemp, opium, cultivated thyme, oregano and sandalwood in 20% concentration and wood tincture were applied sweet, respectively colloidal copper solution at 96 h After 96 h from inoculation with *Candida albicans*, of all the substances used in the studio, only oregano oil inhibited the development of candida.

Figure 7(a, b, c). Culture plates inoculated with *Candida albicans* to which essential oils of musk (white), cinnamon, geranium, hemp (a) opium, cultivated thyme, oregano and sandalwood were applied in a concentration of 20 % and licorice tincture, respectively copper colloidal solution (b), sandalwood oil and oregano oil (c) at 120 h After 5 days of inoculation with *Candida albicans* only oregano oil shows antifungal action (see Fig .7).

Discussion

After 24 h and 72 h from seeding, we made slides stained with methylene blue, which we analyzed under the optical microscope, with the objective of 40x. We found the following:

- The colloidal copper solution partially inhibited the mycotic colonies in the first 24 hours, then we noticed the growth of *Candida albicans* in the following hours on the culture medium, both macroscopically and microscopically.
- Cinnamon oil partially inhibited the culture in the first 24 h, culture that reappeared on the medium after 48 h.
- Geranium oil inhibited the growth of the culture for 24 h, *Candida Albicans* then growing on the medium after 48 h.
- The oils of sandalwood, white musk, opium as well as licorice tincture were not active in the treatment of candida during the 5 days the candida colonies were growing.
- Oregano oil determined the total inhibition of the culture, observing the absence of *Candida albicans* colonies under the microscope as well as on the medium until the end of 120 h.

Conclusions

During the 120 h it can be observed that only oregano oil maintained its inhibition capacity, compared to the other oils: white musk, cinnamon, geranium, hemp, opium, cultivated thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*) and sandalwood in concentration of 20%, as well as liquorice tincture (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* roots), respectively colloidal copper solution.

It can be observed that the essential oil of cultivated thyme is less effective than the essential oil of thyme used in another experiment. Thus, the essential oil of cultivated thyme cannot stop the development of candida even in the first 24 h compared to the essential oil of thyme that was effective during the 3 days analyzed in the previous study.

It is also observed in the case of the cinnamon oil, even the geranium oil and the colloidal copper solution that during the 120 h, the candida remained at the same level, which leads us to the idea that the cinnamon oils

and geranium, as well as colloidal copper solution, used in higher concentrations, could successfully inhibit the development of candida.

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